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Privacy Preservation in Kubernetes-based Federated Learning: A Networking Approach

Abstract—Federated Learning (FL) is a distributed Machine Learning paradigm that enables multiple clients to collaboratively train a model under the control of a central server while preserving data locally in heterogeneous edge devices. To facilitate scalable deployment of FL systems, cloud computing and container-based approaches such as Kubernetes (K8s) have been recently proposed. K8s enables container orchestration for cloud and edge applications while reducing workload management complexity in FL ecosystems. Nonetheless, K8s can violate fundamental FL privacy principles, e.g., the inherent flat networking approach in K8s can potentially allow FL clients to access other client or domain resources. The latter poses an open research problem and gap in the literature because serious privacy risks can arise from attackers gaining access to any client in the FL setup. To address this problem, this paper presents a *networking* approach via *network isolation* at the link layer level, and *authentication* and *data packet encryption* at the network layer level. The former allows to create secure resource sharing, and the latter is used to protect in-transit data. For this purpose, we use a K8s networking operator and a secure network protocol suite. The above combination facilitates on-demand link-layer connectivity, per-link data source authentication, and confidentiality between FL actors. We tested our approach on a network testbed composed of different geo-located nodes where FL clients are deployed. Our promising results showcase the feasibility of the solution for privacy preservation at the network level in K8s-based FL.

Index Terms—Federated Learning, Kubernetes, Networking, Privacy Preservation, Scalability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Federated Learning (FL) is a popular Machine Learning (ML) technique for training models on decentralised, sensitive data while preserving data privacy [1]. This paradigm allows local nodes to collaboratively train a shared model and use it for a given task (e.g., classification or regression) while keeping the data *locally* without sharing their direct information with the FL server [2].

A traditional centralised FL architecture describes cooperation between a central server and heterogeneous clients, aiming to reduce the loss and increase the model prediction accuracy over non-independent and identically distributed (non-iid) data [3]. A typical example of a centralised FL setup is depicted in Fig. 1a, where individual hospitals (e.g., A and B) benefit from the datasets of multiple non-affiliated clients (e.g., A1 and AN in the case of Hospital B) without centralising the data in one place to tackle privacy concerns [4]. A central server hospital updates a global model with only training results (i.e., parameters) which are aggregated and exchanged at a certain frequency within the clients. We emulate this scenario and treat this use case as a running example.

Fig. 1: Running example of Kubernetes-based FL

Due to the heterogeneous nature of multiple decentralised clients, it is challenging to implement and deploy FL systems over various clients that are spanned in different geographical locations [5]. Adopting cloud computing technologies such as containers and *Kubernetes* (K8s) is a promising approach to increase computation elasticity and efficiency when deploying distributed ML architectures, such as FL, at both near the edge and data centres [6], [7], [8], [9]. A container is a standalone, lightweight, executable software package, which includes the application code and all the necessary data for its execution [10]. Packaging FL tasks with containers can reduce the complexity of managing the underlying technology stack for users [7]. K8s is a container workload orchestration system for simplifying and automating application deployment, scaling, migration, and management across distributed nodes [5], [7]. However, given the cloud native methodology followed by K8s, a flat networking approach is imposed where all pods (the minimal unit of deployment in K8s, composed of one or more containers belonging to the same network) can communicate with each other [11].

Nevertheless, the above-mentioned approach *contradicts FL privacy* principles, namely, zero knowledge, and data reachability and accessibility in Secure Multiparty Computation (SMC) [3], [4]. These principles aim to describe that data should be *only* accessed, consumed and processed by its producer in order to tackle privacy risks to personal data leakage, misuse, and abuse [9], [2]. This is in line with the regulations in collecting and managing data across heterogeneous sources described in the EU/UK General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [2]. In our running example, in Fig. 1b, by deploying FL using K8s for scalability and workload management, a flat network is created allowing the reachability of resources between hospitals which violates FL privacy concerns.

The main contribution of this paper lies in tackling the previously described privacy-preserving challenges in K8s-based FL from a networking perspective. We propose a networking

and data-link management approach. Our design employs *network isolation* to ensure security control in resource sharing communication [12], and *authentication and packet encryption* to address privacy risks native to K8s flat networking. From a technical, implementation and testing point, our contributions can be summarised as:

- 1) **Network isolation & packet authentication and encryption in K8s-based FL:** We use the Link Layer Secure connectivity for Microservice platforms (L2S-M) operator [11] and the Internet Protocol Security (IPsec) protocol suite [13] for privacy-preserving in FL deployed using K8s. This tries to tackle privacy from a data-in-transit perspective different to common FL application-level approaches like secure aggregation combined with HTTPS [3], [2]. Communication between clients and the server is also critical in FL processes, introducing another vulnerability surface [1].
- 2) **Proof-of-concept implementation environment:** We deploy a two-site implementation in different geographical locations, along with multiple collaborative clients with a task from the medical domain using the Medical MNIST image classification dataset [14].
- 3) **Network and ML performance evaluation:** We study network isolation, throughput and added overheads on the network side, and classification accuracy and loss on the ML side. To study scalability merits, we performed experiments with 10, 30 and 50 clients distributed in the two geographical locations. Results are promising, exhibiting good feasibility properties empowering privacy preservation in an FL deployment facilitated by K8s.

The rest of the document is organised as follows, Section II shows concepts needed to understand the present document and work related to this paper. Section III describes the proposed approach for network isolation and data packets encryption in FL. The experimentation, implementation, and discussion are presented in Section IV. Finally, the conclusions and future work are presented in Section V.

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A. Privacy Preservation in FL

Privacy is one of the essential properties of FL [3]. In FL, no private data is shared among the clients and the central server [6]. Nonetheless, even though data is not shared, ML models trained on personal data and transferred over the network have been shown to leak information about users that can be exploited in privacy attacks [9], [2]. Therefore, privacy preservation and security for FL is an ongoing topic in the research community [3], [4].

Privacy preservation in FL is commonly addressed from an application point of view. For example, secure aggregation, differential privacy, and clustering are used to mitigate data and model poisoning, inference, and backdoor attacks, among other privacy threats [4], [3], [15]. However, securing the network and in-transit data is an essential ingredient to allow privacy preservation in an FL setup. Only a few works in the

literature have focused their efforts on investigating network-level risks and countermeasures in FL [1]. In the present paper, a networking approach is proposed to target privacy preservation in K8s-based FL.

B. K8s-based ML and FL

K8s is an open-source solution for automating the deployment, scaling, and management of workloads of containerised applications [9]. K8s can simplify the deployment and maintenance of applications and compute loads, especially the training and hosting of ML models [16]. Different works have demonstrated the benefits of using containerised approaches to deploy ML pipelines. For example, the authors of [7] propose a flexible container-based architecture for scalable ML setups. The focus of this architecture is to reduce the barriers to the development and deployment of the entire ML life-cycle. Similarly, Wan et al. [16] propose a K8s-based platform for online ML targeting IoT and fog computing scenarios.

K8s have also started to be a choice for deploying FL systems given their distributed and scalable nature. For example, Kim et al. [5] present KubeFL to help the deployment of the FL over multiple clients via K8s. The authors perform measurement-based analysis of the implementation on edge devices such as NVIDIA Jetson TX2 under various practical configurations. Likewise, in [8], the authors propose the design and development of server-client cooperation framework for FL using container-related technologies. However, none of these works have addressed the flat networking approach of the cloud-native K8s nor the security and privacy aspects required for FL deployment which is targeted in this paper.

C. Implications of K8s Networking

Notwithstanding the advantages that K8s brings to FL environments in the cloud and edge scenarios, the literature has barely addressed the privacy concerns that these solutions could introduce in production environments. The most relevant issue comes from one of the multiple abstraction layers that K8s uses to simplify the development and deployment of containerised workloads, i.e., its networking model. K8s imposes a set of restrictions that any third-party networking solutions (developed as networking plugins for K8s) must follow. It requires that pods can communicate with all other pods on any K8s node without Network Address Translation (NAT) [17]. In consequence, to preserve this model, popular networking plugins like Flannel¹ and Calico² implement flat-networking, with all pods being able to reach each other at the IP layer, regardless of their location in the cluster.

This flat-networking model could adversely affect the privacy of the data shared within a cluster since all containers can directly see each other. Potentially, malicious elements could communicate with genuine FL clients holding sensitive information, which could lead to privacy-related attacks. One way to mitigate this risk is to create virtual networks that only certain clients are able to attach to, enabling communication

¹Flannel: <https://github.com/flannel-io/flannel>

²Calico: <https://www.tigera.io/project-calico>

only between pods connected to the same virtual network. However, K8s *does not natively* support this behaviour.

Gonzalez et al. in [11] attempted to solve this problem by enabling *virtual networking in K8s* clusters, allowing to isolate containerised workloads. The authors presented an open-source solution, the L2S-M operator ³, that allows the creation of link-layer virtual networks in such a way that the containers attached to them are located in the same broadcast domain regardless of their location in the cluster. This enables building L2 container network administrative domains that containers use to communicate with each other. Although initially designed for Small Unmanned Aerial Vehicle scenarios, this approach can be used in cloud and edge environments to provide the desired behaviour in FL scenarios.

III. A NETWORKING APPROACH FOR PRIVACY PRESERVATION IN KUBERNETES-BASED FL

Data transmission between clients and server are crucial in FL. In this distributed ML approach, a global model is learned in rounds with contributions from multiple networked parties and orchestrated by a central node. Therefore, the network represents another surface of vulnerability. This can be exacerbated when enabling multiple access routes to resources in the system between all nodes, which is natively allowed in K8s. In this work, we propose the establishment of link-layer connectivity among the different components of an FL solution in a K8s deployment to support on-demand network isolation for privacy preservation. In addition, we also propose data packet encryption to provide confidentiality to in-transit data at the network level for privacy augmentation. Next, we discuss the aforementioned aspects in detail.

A. Network isolation

To preserve user privacy and resources in an FL setup deployed in a K8s cluster, we propose to create logically isolated network partitions overlaid on top of a common physical network infrastructure. The main idea is that each partition is isolated from others by a set of policies defined by the K8s networking operator, which allows the administrators to easily create and modify the isolated virtual networks on-demand at the link layer level. It is important to define the expected initial isolation level (e.g., per domain or node) as well as design dynamic isolation mechanisms that can enforce the isolation level of any given service. We use L2S-M operator [11] to provide network isolation on an FL setup deployed in a K8s cluster. In principle, L2S-M allows the provision of network connectivity as a service by deploying a data plane that containers can use to establish link-layer connectivity between the pods. In this case, each pod inside the cluster will be attached to one or several virtual network(s) (created beforehand) and exclusively communicate with the members attached to the same network. This in turn provides security against malicious pods that could be deployed inside the cluster. More precisely, such malicious pods will not

be able to communicate with the FL pods unless they are attached to the same administrative domain (virtual network). We discuss how the isolation is performed in a later subsection.

B. Data packets authentication and encryption

Eavesdrop and replay attacks can occur when an adversary intercepts network messages, and then fraudulently sniffs, suppresses, or replays them to mislead the receiver to carry out the adversary's intended activity [4]. Given the networked-system nature of FL, it is crucial to enable a secure communication medium for the information exchanged between local clients and the server on the network layer. For this purpose, we propose the use of the IPsec [13] framework to ensure secure communications against attacks that may be launched from outside the K8s cluster (since the L2 isolation already provides a security layer against malicious pods within the cluster). We use the Encapsulating Security Payload (ESP) security protocol for encryption and integrity protection of the packets. To establish an IPsec tunnel, we use the Internet Key Exchange (IKE) protocol. IPsec in Transport Mode is used, preserving the original IP header. IKE builds the secure tunnels and ESP provides authentication, integrity, and confidentiality in communications between the hosts where the FL server and clients are deployed.

This encryption must be performed between the hosts (i.e., the nodes of the K8s cluster) since the IP addresses of the FL containers can dynamically change, which hinders the direct implementation of IPsec between FL clients and the server. This can cause a scalability issue in large K8s clusters since every node must establish a tunnel between all the members of a cluster.

C. Proposed Architecture

The proposed architecture for this FL environment is illustrated in Fig. 2. This architecture uses an open-source K8s network operator (L2S-M) to establish a virtual network and link-layer connectivity between the FL clients and/or the server. The network operator requires the deployment of one virtualised programmable L2 switch in every node of the cluster. In order to interconnect these L2 switches in the cluster, the proposed architecture relies on IP tunneling techniques to build point-to-point links using Virtual Extensible Local Area Networks (VXLANs) [18]. Each VXLAN is first built in the host and afterward, attached inside the virtualised L2 switch. These VXLANs are only built between some of the nodes of the cluster rather than a mesh architecture to provide more flexibility to accommodate the necessities of different architectures and/or services. The creation of these links between the switches results in a programmable link-layer overlay, allowing traffic to be sent as if all nodes were located in the same Local Area Network (LAN), i.e., the same broadcast domain.

The network operator's control logic dictates how the pods are attached to the switch by listening to the API events of K8s. Inside each pod, a new interface will be available to be used for this communication, while leaving the default K8s interface

³L2S-M: <http://l2sm.io>

Fig. 2: Proposed FL architecture with isolated L2 connectivity, and L3 encryption in a K8s cluster.

intact (i.e., the interface provided by the networking plugin used in the cluster). In consequence, the solution extends the K8s networking without sacrificing its main advantages and abstraction layers.

Since each switch can be programmed to support the use of Virtual Local Area Networks (VLANs) tags, our model uses this technique to perform network isolation. Each L2 switch port assigns a different VLAN tag to specific ports based on the allowed links, creating separated container networks. These tags will be aggregated to the Ethernet frames generated by the pods, and the receiving switches will only forward those that belong to the same tag of each port (instead of performing a broadcast), isolating members belonging to different virtual networks. For example, it will never allow a member of one zone of the clusters to reach another portion of the cluster.

Thanks to the use of this programmable overlay, it is not necessary to introduce IPsec between all members of the cluster, thereby mitigating the scalability problem described in the previous subsection for traffic encryption. As traffic from the pods is only going to traverse the VXLAN tunnels built between neighbours, these links are the only ones that need to be secured. Therefore, it is not mandatory to integrate IPsec between all nodes, but only between the nodes that are connected by a VXLAN. This in turn not only reduces the number of tunnels needed to be established in the cluster but also the complexity of aggregating new nodes to a cluster that can enable building new tunnels for securing FL data.

IV. CASE STUDY

We demonstrate the proposed architecture feasibility with a case study prototype implementation for image classification using medical images in an FL K8s setup.

A. Datasets, models, and tasks

We use the image classification *Medical MNIST* [14] dataset consisting of 64×64 sized grayscale images. The dataset contains 58954 images of six classes (i.e., types): abdomen Computed Tomography (CT); breast magnetic resonance imaging

Fig. 3: Medical MNIST dataset [14]

(MRI); chest X-Ray; chest CT; hand X-Ray; and head CT. Figure 3 shows the different classes. The dataset is randomly split into 80% training and 20% test split. We use Latent Dirichlet Allocation (LDA) to generate a *non-iid* version of the dataset. LDA is a commonly used technique [3] for emulating real-world FL scenarios where each client owns different data.

We employ a simple convolutional neural network (CNN) comprised of 4 convolutional layers with 32, 64, 128 and 256 feature maps respectively and a kernel size of 3, followed by a 2×2 max pooling after each layer. For the classification, two fully connected layers of 256 and 128 neurons were used, respectively. In order to build the FL pipeline, the *Flower*⁴ framework was used and deployed in a *K8s cluster*. Flower enables development and evaluation of FL systems adopted by major research organisations across academia and industry[15]. Flower allows the federation of any workload while being agnostic to the underlying ML framework (e.g., TensorFlow or PyTorch) and programming language (e.g., Python or C++) [15]. We use the popular FedAVG algorithm [3] for model aggregation.

B. Scenarios and experiments definition

We demonstrate the viability of our proposed approach in different scenarios based on the running example of Fig. 1. Two hospitals with multiple user clients are part of an FL setup. First, we tested an FL setup using a commonly used networking plugin in K8s, namely *Flannel*, to corroborate the claims of the *flat networking* approach of K8s. Then, we conducted testing with data packet encryption using IPsec.

⁴Flower: <https://flower.dev/>

Finally, we deploy a complete implementation solution using K8s, L2S-M for network isolation, and IPsec for data packet encryption. Two different experiments were performed using these scenarios. They are described next.

1) *Experiment 1– network isolation*: We compare connectivity across different setups in terms of network *isolation* using an instance of the example application containing one central server and two sets of five independent clients deployed in a K8s cluster. Each client or server corresponds to a single independent pod detailed in Sec. IV-C.

All deployed pods exchange *ICMP echo packets* using GNU’s *ping* implementation through the default K8s container network interface. The latter is configured by the Flannel plugin in a standard K8s cluster installation. After changing to the interface configured with L2S-M, we repeat the same process. Based on the received *ICMP echo reply* we can determine two distinct connectivity matrices and compare network isolation back by the solution approach to the standard K8s alternative.

2) *Experiment 2– FL and system performance analysis*: We explore the model-related qualitative impact of our approach on FL processes including the predictions accuracy and corresponding loss or penalties after bad predictions, converge time, communication throughput between the server and clients, and client scalability. We ran multiple FL experiments using the different system configurations previously mentioned: Vanilla K8s, K8s with data-packet encryption, and a complete configuration of K8s with network isolation and data-packet encryption. To test scalability, we use a setup of 10, 30, and 50 clients that are trained for 20 FL rounds using the aforementioned different system configurations.

C. Proof-of-concept implementation

We present a K8s-based FL implementation over an actual testbed setup shown in Fig. 4. The testbed for running all the experiments is managed by a private OpenStack⁵ instance. The physical locations are scattered in two different geo-locations to replicate the scenario of the running example. A K8s cluster, consisting of one controller node and three working nodes was deployed. To reduce the need for resources, the controller node also runs the FL server, as part of the domain belonging to the shared central service (using the 10.244.0.0/24 network), and has 15vCPUs, 25GB of RAM and 100GB of disk space. The worker nodes have 15vCPUs, 15GB of RAM and 100GB of storage. Worker node 1 is part of the Hospital A administrative domain, that uses the 10.244.1.0/24 network. Worker nodes 2 and 3 are part of Hospital B administrative domain, which is comprised by networks 10.244.2.0/24 and 10.244.3.0/24 respectively. Both domains belong to the same K8s cluster as a FL deployment. Various FL clients can run in the different worker nodes depending on the experiment performed. To test our approach, the networking is managed by the L2S-M operator and IPsec is used in transport mode to encrypt the communications between workers and the server.

⁵Openstack: <https://www.openstack.org/>

Fig. 4: Experimental setup.

(a) Flat network imposed by K8s. (b) Isolated network via L2S-M.

Fig. 5: Connectivity matrix for different system configurations. Clients enumerated from 1 to 10. Server identified by S.

D. Evaluation results

1) *Experiment 1 – network isolation*: Connectivity matrices in Fig. 5 portray flat networking in a standard K8s deployment with Flannel (or similar container networking plugins) interconnecting all deployed pods regardless of the assigned network. This means that each pod in this setup can communicate not only with the central server and the other pods belonging to the same domain but also with any other domain attached to the cluster. During a security breach, access to different domains can potentially widen the attack surface.

On the contrary, the L2S-M implementation effectively creates separated networks that *cannot* communicate with each other. The separation causes packets across domains to be simply isolated at the network level. The only pod that can communicate with all other ones is the central server in compliance with FL standards, noting that the server cannot use its internal IP stack to re-route packets to preserve isolation. Since the separation is enforced at the network level, this result could be extrapolated to an arbitrary number of clients per domain.

2) *Experiment 2 – FL and system performance analysis*: Different dimensions were analysed in this experiment in terms of FL performance. These dimensions are:

- **Model accuracy**: In this image classification task, the accuracy of whether an image is labelled in the correct class or not, is the main metric for analysing the results of the learning task. Using the system’s different configurations mentioned in Sec. IV-B, an evaluation for different numbers of FL clients was performed. Figure 6 shows the results: 6a, 6b, 6c, depict the accuracy for 10, 30 and

Fig. 6: Accuracy of the results for (a) 10, (b) 30, and (c) 50 clients in the different system configurations.

Fig. 7: Loss of the model predictions for (a) 10, (b) 30, and (c) 50 clients in the different system configurations.

50 clients, respectively in this FL setup. As exhibited, the results are congruent in a range of 99.5 ± 0.1 when converged for all the configurations and different numbers of clients.

- Model loss:** Similar to the previous dimension, analysing the loss of the model predictions is a key metric to evaluate if an ML model has learned the desired features. The loss represents a penalty when a classification is incorrect. The smaller the loss the better. Accordingly, the analysis was performed using different scenarios and numbers of clients. The results of the experimentation are shown in Fig. 7. The loss reduced from a starting loss of 0.16 ± 0.02 in episode 1 to 0.03 ± 0.01 for every scenario and system configuration.
- Time to converge:** Another important aspect when developing and deploying FL systems is the execution time until convergence. For all the experiments, the execution time was measured during 20 FL rounds using the Flower server statistics. The results are shown in Table I. The execution times are incrementally ranging from 11479.41 seconds (s) for a run of 10 clients in a K8s-only configuration to 61168.84s for a run of 50 clients in a complete configuration of K8s, IPsec and L2S-M.
- Throughput:** As mentioned along this document, communications play a crucial role in FL systems. For this reason, we analyse if the proposed approach introduces any limitations regarding throughput measured in the central server. Fig. 8a, 8b, and 8c show the transmitted bytes in runs of 10, 30 and 50 clients using the different system configurations. The rates are similar for all the schemes with sporadic peaks. The average of transmitted bytes for 10 clients using the complete approach (i.e., K8s, IPsec and L2S-M) is 56713.291 bytes, for 30 clients is 82961.24 bytes, and for 50 is 96523.54 bytes.

TABLE I: Execution times in Seconds (s) using the proposed approach with different systems configurations: Only K8s, K8s and IPsec, K8s, IPsec and L2S-M.

Clients	System configurations		
	K8s	K8s and IPsec	K8s, IPsec and L2S-M
10	11479.41s	11587.16s	11672.74s
30	41933.88s	42090.24s	42118.59s
50	60905.23s	61085.59s	61168.84s

E. Discussion

The results from the experiments conducted showed the feasibility of the approach for privacy preservation in K8s-based FL. By combining L2S-M and IPsec, is possible to enable network isolation on demand and encrypt data packets in communications between the different FL actors. Isolation is created on demand targeting only intended FL clients. In the proposed approach, isolation can be defined by the domain, location, or host of the FL client. Experiment 1 showcased this capability. The results describe how, using our approach, clients can have only access to resources within the same hospital of the running example. Otherwise, given the flat networking approach of K8s, they can reach resources from everywhere in the cluster (i.e., Hospital A, Hospital B, and the central server). Consequently, if one domain is compromised, an additional security layer will be in place, working to prevent eventual attackers from interfering with the other domains.

Experiment 2 focused on analysing the costs incurred in terms of performance while adding these capabilities to FL systems deployed using K8s. The analysed dimensions were model accuracy and loss, time to converge, and throughput in different networking scenarios with different numbers of clients for scalability purposes. There were no significant effects when using the proposed approach on system performance.

Fig. 8: Throughput for (a) 10, (b) 30, and (c) 50 clients in the different system configurations.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

FL is one of the most promising ML approaches to collaborative training and learning ML models in a privacy-preserving fashion. K8s can be exploited for scalable and manageable FL. However, some challenges arise when using K8s with its flat networking approach, which can present a risk for privacy preservation in FL. In order to guarantee the privacy of user data, it is crucial to leverage privacy-preserving mechanisms in every vulnerability surface. In this paper, we focused on providing privacy-augmentation approaches at the network level in K8s-based FL.

We propose the creation of on-demand link layer connectivity between FL actors for the establishment and provisioning of network isolation. Using the L2S-M controller, this approach reassures that only targeted clients have access to local resources in this cloud-native environment. Additionally, we propose the use of data-packets encryption to provide data source authentication and confidentiality. This is enabled by the use of the IPsec protocol suite to encrypt in-transit data at the network level. We have tested our approach in different scenarios studying the feasibility, scalability and accuracy of the proposed architecture. Our promising results show that the approach does not affect the FL system in terms of performance (i.e., ML accuracy and loss) nor limits the throughput between clients and the server. There is a small overhead when using the solution of around 2-3% of training time, although, this can be neglected considering the benefits of privacy-preservation of the approach.

It is envisioned that distributed learning approaches such as FL will be key enablers for 6G networks. Our future research directions will focus on scalable, sustainable, and trustworthy FL for 6G. We plan to leverage Differential Privacy (DP) to provide further privacy guarantees to participating clients in containerised environments. DP noise can be introduced at different stages of the FL system and at the K8s level. Furthermore, we have focused our efforts on intra-cluster communication, future work will include privacy-preserving implementations for inter-cluster and multi-tenant communications towards a secure, scalable grid-computing approach.

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